

The One-Stop Shop and Integrated One-Stop Shop Mechanisms: A Solution for Reforming Administrative Procedures for Students at Vietnamese Universities

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Abstract

Administrative procedures for students at universities in Vietnam are extremely important to their learning and research process. These procedures are found in the regulations, rules, and internal guidelines that students must follow while studying at the university. Currently, administrative procedures for students at Vietnamese universities are quite cumbersome, both in terms of the number of procedures to be completed and the complexity of the process. This causes considerable difficulties for students and student support staff. This article will focus on analyzing the current state of administrative procedures for students and propose the development of a one-stop shop or integrated one-stop shop mechanism at Vietnamese universities.

Keywords: *One-stop mechanism, integrated one-stop service, administrative procedure reform.*

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Introduction

In current university administration, administrative procedures for students at Vietnamese universities are extremely important, directly impacting the quality of learning, research, and student experience. This is not only a tool for university management but also a decisive activity in building a professional and effective learning environment. However, in practice, the implementation of administrative procedures for students at Vietnamese universities currently receives relatively low satisfaction ratings from students due to their cumbersome nature, numerous steps, and lack of automation, causing confusion for both students and administrators. Administrative regulations within universities, although designed to control and ensure order, lack flexibility, leading to students having to spend a significant amount of time and effort to comply. This not only reduces the efficiency of administrative staff but also negatively impacts students' learning and research processes, diminishing satisfaction and creating a gap between the university and students.

Some universities have made efforts to reform administrative procedures; however, the solutions implemented so far have not truly addressed the root of the problem,

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especially the lack of synchronization in processes and coordination mechanisms between units within the university. Therefore, the issue of administrative procedure reform at universities in Vietnam is not only urgent but also requires a comprehensive solution, with the participation of stakeholders from state management levels to educational institutions and students.

In this context, the application of a "one-stop shop" mechanism at universities is considered a highly feasible solution to minimize cumbersome procedures, improve the efficiency of administrative departments, and, more importantly, enhance the quality of education and student satisfaction throughout their studies. This mechanism not only optimizes administrative management processes but also creates a flexible communication and coordination system between units within the university, minimizing delays and overlapping information, and increasing transparency in university operations.

This article will analyze the current state of administrative procedures for students at universities in Vietnam, pointing out existing problems and limitations in the current administrative management system, and proposing the development of a "one-stop shop" or "integrated one-stop shop" mechanism as a core element. The goal is to build an efficient administrative system, minimize unnecessary activities, and create favorable conditions for students and functional departments within the university.

Theoretical Basis

Concepts of Administrative Procedures and Administrative Procedure Reform

According to the Vietnamese Dictionary: "Administrative procedures in administrative law include norms regulating the organization, powers, and duties of state agencies and the rights and obligations of citizens and social organizations in the field of state administrative management. These norms constitute administrative law in terms of content. Besides these norms, there are also many norms regulating the procedures and forms in resolving citizens' requests to state administrative agencies or requests within state administrative agencies. Administrative procedures are very diverse, but can be divided into two basic types: 1) Procedures for carrying out tasks related to the internal relations of state agencies. 2) Procedures for carrying out tasks related to the relations of state agencies with citizens and social organizations. Each type of procedure includes many specific procedures applied to each type of task and each field of management. Administrative procedures in relation to citizens include two important types: a) Administrative procedures in the work of state agencies "a) State agencies consider and resolve the legitimate subjective rights of citizens in cases where citizens sue a state agency. b) Administrative procedures in which competent agencies consider issues of administrative responsibility and impose penalties for violations by citizens. Also known as administrative violation handling procedures or administrative litigation." (National Council for the Compilation of the Vietnamese Encyclopedia, 2005).

Clause 1, Article 3 of Government Decree 63/2010/ND-CP dated June 8, 2010, on administrative procedure control stipulates: "Administrative procedure" is the sequence, method of implementation, documents, requirements, and conditions prescribed by state agencies or competent authorities to resolve a specific matter related to individuals or organizations.

Regarding "administrative procedure reform," based on Section III, Article 1 of Resolution 76/NQ-CP dated July 15, 2021, issued by the Government on the overall program for state administrative reform for the period 2021-2030, the specific tasks for state administrative reform for the period 2021-2030 focus on six areas, namely:

- Institutional reform;
- Reforming administrative procedures;
- Reforming the state administrative apparatus;
- Reforming the civil service system;
- Public finance reform;
- Building and developing e-government and digital government.

Thus, administrative procedure reform can be understood as one of the six tasks of Vietnam's administrative reform in the period 2021-2030. Administrative procedure reform involves reforming legal regulations on the order and procedures for exercising the authority of state administrative agencies and authorized persons; reforming regulations on various types of administrative procedures; and reforming the implementation of administrative procedures.

Administrative Procedures at the University

The University of Oslo's website in Norway defines administrative procedures as follows: "Administrative procedures at a university are governed by administrative acts. These acts can be found in regulations, rules, internal guidelines, implementation guidelines, individual decisions, and appeals." (University of Oslo, 2006).

In Vietnam, based on the concept of administrative procedures, administrative procedures at universities can be understood as follows: Administrative procedures at universities are the processes, conditions, documents, and requirements that the university's management units implement to handle specific tasks related to students, faculty, and other units within the framework of educational and administrative laws. These procedures may include reviewing academic records, issuing diplomas, handling student violations of regulations, or other internal administrative procedures within the university. Each administrative procedure at a university is regulated in detail regarding the order of implementation, specific conditions, and requirements, aiming to ensure transparency, efficiency, and legality in the educational management process.

Concepts of the One-Stop Shop and Integrated One-Stop Shop Mechanism

Article 11 of the 2001 Law on Administrative Reform states: "The one-stop mechanism is a method of handling administrative work for citizens and organizations at a single point of contact within a state agency, whereby citizens and organizations only need to submit documents in one place and receive results in another, helping to minimize inconvenience and delays."

Clause 1, Article 2 of Government Decree No. 63/2010/ND-CP dated June 8, 2010, on administrative procedure control states: "The integrated one-stop mechanism is a method of resolving administrative procedures in which relevant state administrative agencies coordinate to resolve administrative procedures of citizens and organizations involving multiple state agencies, thereby minimizing overlap and wasted time for citizens and organizations."

Paragraphs 1 and 2, Article 4, Decree No. 61/2018/ND-CP dated April 23, 2018 on the implementation of the one-stop shop and integrated one-stop shop mechanism in resolving administrative procedures:

- "The one-stop mechanism for resolving administrative procedures is a method of receiving applications, resolving and returning results of administrative procedures, monitoring, supervising, and evaluating the resolution of administrative procedures for organizations and individuals by a competent agency through the One-Stop Service Department as stipulated in Clause 3 of this Article."
- "The integrated one-stop mechanism for resolving administrative procedures is a method of coordination between competent authorities in receiving applications, resolving and returning results for an administrative procedure or a group of related administrative procedures, monitoring, supervising, and evaluating the resolution of administrative procedures for organizations and individuals through the One-Stop Service Department as stipulated in Clause 3 of this Article."

Both mechanisms aim to reform administrative procedures, creating convenience, transparency, and reducing complex administrative processes for citizens and organizations.

Administrative Procedures for Students at Vietnamese Universities

Based on the nature of university operations, administrative procedures for students are the methods used to implement the requirements of the Ministry of Education and Training and other stakeholders regarding academic, research, and community service activities that students must fulfill throughout their time at university.

Within the scope of this article, the author only addresses the administrative procedures that students must follow from admission to graduation, which involve multiple units and departments in the process, such as:

- a) Types of administrative procedures in the admission and training process: Transfer procedures; Deferral procedures; Procedures for considering leave of absence, withdrawal from studies, and continuation of studies due to personal wishes; Procedures for changing training majors; Procedures for issuing and certifying graduation diplomas; Procedures for reissuing and adjusting diplomas and certificates.
- b) Types of administrative procedures in student affairs: Procedures for considering awards for students and trainees; Procedures for considering disciplinary actions; Procedures for evaluating student performance; Procedures for considering the awarding of scholarships to encourage learning; Procedures for implementing tuition fee exemptions and reductions.

Current state of Administrative Procedures for Students at Vietnamese Universities

Throughout their studies at university, students will encounter a range of diverse and complex administrative procedures, such as: enrollment, deferment, transfer, graduation review, and diploma issuance. In practice, these procedures at universities require many steps and necessitate students providing complete documentation such as application forms, transcripts, and confirmations from relevant departments. However, a major weakness is the lack of standardization among universities. Each university applies its own procedures and forms, creating difficulties for students, especially when transferring or deferring their studies.

At the Foreign Trade University, when students need to withdraw from their studies, take a temporary leave of absence, re-enroll after a period of deferment, or transfer to another university, in addition to providing an application form, they must also obtain confirmation from relevant departments such as the Finance and Planning Department, the Library, and their homeroom teacher. (Foreign Trade University, 2024).

At the Dong Nai branch of the Vietnam National University of Forestry, students wishing to transfer must first have a transfer agency; then obtain a confirmation letter from the Rector (this step will be handled by the transferring university); after receiving the Rector's confirmation, students go to the Admissions Department, Training Office to submit their application; and finally, after the Training Office notifies the student of the results by phone, the student must go to the Training Office to receive the transfer decision, then go to the Political and Student Affairs Office to withdraw their documents and contact the transferring university to complete the enrollment procedures. This procedure requires students to go through four steps and contact three supporting agencies. (Vietnam National University of Forestry, Dong Nai branch, 2026).

At Phenikaa University, the procedure for deferring studies involves the following steps: Students submit a deferral application, which must be signed by the student and agreed upon by their parents. Step 2: Students obtain confirmation from their class advisor and the Faculty leadership. Step 3: Students fulfill their obligations to the University through the Library Center and the Dormitory Management Board. Step 4: Students go to the Training Department to confirm the total number of registered credits. Step 5: Students pay any applicable fees and tuition (if any) at the Finance and Accounting Department and receive confirmation upon completion. Step 6: Students return to the Training Department to request confirmation of the deleted registered credits. Step 7: Students prepare and submit the necessary documents to the Student Affairs Department. Therefore, at Phenikaa University, students must complete seven steps when applying for a deferral, including contacting seven different support units for confirmation. (Phenikaa University, 2021).

Establish a One-Stop Shop and Integrated One-Stop Shop Mechanism at Vietnamese Universities

The one-stop shop mechanism at universities is designed to provide maximum support to students in accessing and handling administrative procedures, while ensuring more convenient and efficient communication between students and the university. The main goal is to create a friendly, open, and transparent environment, saving time and simplifying the process of carrying out administrative procedures.

By clearly defining responsibilities and handling requirements for each student request, this mechanism not only improves service quality but also facilitates more effective coordination among functional units within the university. This ensures that all student requests and inquiries are addressed promptly and in accordance with regulations, contributing to an enhanced learning experience and student satisfaction throughout their studies at the university.

This mechanism not only serves students in resolving administrative procedures at their schools, but also aims to implement Resolution No. 29-NQ-TW of the 8th Central Committee Meeting of the 11th Party Congress on fundamental and

comprehensive reform of education and training, meeting the requirements of industrialization and modernization in the context of a socialist-oriented market economy and international integration; standardizing the teaching staff and management personnel, management mechanisms, facilities and other conditions to ensure the quality of education; and publicly disclosing the results of measuring the level of satisfaction of citizens and students with the services provided by educational institutions.

To build a successful and efficient one-stop service mechanism, universities in Vietnam should refer to the one-stop service model at Vinh University. On June 16, 2016, the Rector of Vinh University signed Decision No. 706/QĐ-DHV, promulgating the Regulations on the implementation of the one-stop service mechanism at Vinh University. Based on the principle of publicly disclosing administrative procedures, resolving them promptly within the proper authority, in accordance with regulations and laws; the one-stop service department is responsible for receiving requests and delivering results, ensuring close coordination between functional units. Vinh University has selected 24 administrative procedures for pilot implementation at the one-stop service department, including: students requesting to withdraw from school; students requesting temporary leave of absence; students requesting to return to school; students requesting to transfer schools; students requesting compensation for personal injury insurance; Confirmation for student loan applications; requesting confirmation of student referral letters; receiving student files; renewing student passports; students who have not yet received exam scores or request a review of course grading results; requesting confirmation of completion of training programs; correcting student information on the management software. These procedures will be received and processed at the One-Stop Service Department. Staff will provide guidance, receive documents and files, process and return results to students. This department is directly managed and operated by the Student Affairs and Political Education Department. The staff in charge of these tasks all have good professional competence, ethical qualities, dedication to their work, and a high sense of responsibility in handling administrative procedures for students. (Vinh University, 2016).

At Hanoi University of Natural Resources and Environment, a one-stop mechanism has been implemented for handling administrative procedures for students in the following areas: Student Affairs, Health, Training, Finance - Accounting, and Facilities, covering more than 30 administrative procedures. All administrative procedures are received at the One-Stop Service Department and results are returned at the One-Stop Service Department. (Hanoi University of Natural Resources and Environment, 2023).

Besides learning from the experiences of Vinh University and Hanoi University of Natural Resources and Environment, it is crucial to change the perception of university administrators regarding the necessity of establishing a "one-stop shop" or "integrated one-stop shop" mechanism, and the benefits and effectiveness it brings to the university and students. When this understanding is correct, the guidance in building the mechanism will be thorough and effective.

Furthermore, universities also need to promote digital transformation in handling administrative procedures at several stages, such as: online application submission (students submit requests for administrative procedures through the Student Portal or the One-Stop Service Portal using their student accounts); sending confirmation notifications and results of administrative procedures to students via student email. This way, students will not have to go directly to the One-Stop Service Department to

submit applications and wait for results, saving time and effort. Administrative staff can also easily compile and forward documents to the relevant departments, as well as facilitating archiving.

Conclusion

In response to the need for administrative procedure reform and improved management quality at universities, the "one-stop shop" and "integrated one-stop shop" mechanisms are being proposed for widespread implementation. This is considered a comprehensive solution to simplify and increase transparency in administrative procedures, thereby minimizing inconvenience and saving time for students and staff.

The "one-stop shop" mechanism centralizes the processing of all administrative procedures at a single point of contact, while the "integrated one-stop shop" ensures synchronized coordination between departments within the school as well as with external management agencies. The application of information technology plays a key role, automating processes, facilitating online application submissions for students, and tracking processing progress. Simultaneously, procedures will be standardized, eliminating unnecessary regulations, and ensuring transparency and accessibility.

This research focuses on analyzing the current state of administrative procedures for students and proposes the establishment of a one-stop shop and integrated one-stop shop mechanism at Vietnamese universities. It is believed that if universities are determined and focus their efforts on implementing this one-stop shop and integrated one-stop shop mechanism, it will ensure the quality and efficiency of work in coordinating activities between units within the university and enhance student satisfaction as well as the satisfaction of society as a whole.

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